

PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT

Azzamova Umida Alisherovna

Assistant, The department of languages,
Samarkand State Medical University

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ABSTRACT

The A, B, C, D of life are attitude, behavior, character and discipline. A, B, C, D are not only the basic letters of alphabets, they are basic qualities of human being. Good working attitude is important to attain success in one's life. Developing a positive attitude means interpreting life's event in a way that is truthful, honest, and self-affirming. Our behavior is the act we act in general, especially in relation to the situation they are in or the people they are with. Character refers to the sum of an individual's qualities and characteristics which differentiate him or her from others. An individual's character is actually an amalgamation of his or her qualities which makes him unique and helps him stand apart from the rest. Discipline is needed in every aspect. To work or to learn in every aspect, discipline is very important. The important type of disciplines are physical discipline, mental discipline, social discipline and economic discipline. Discipline is needed in every aspect. To work or to learn in every aspect. Discipline is very important. one has to remember that every successful person has a painful story and every painful story has a successful ending.

The A, B, C, D's of life are Attitude, Behavior, Character and Discipline. A, B, C, D are not only the basic letters of alphabet, they are basic qualities of human being. One should maintain The A, B, C, D's of life are Attitude, Behavior, Character and Discipline. A, B, C, D are not only the basic letters of alphabet, they are basic qualities of human being. One should maintain The A, B, C, D's of life are Attitude, Behavior, Character and Discipline. A, B, C, D are not only the basic letters of alphabet, they are basic qualities of human being. One should maintain The A, B, C, D's of life are Attitude, Behavior, Character and Discipline. A, B, C, D are not only the basic letters of alphabet, they are basic qualities of human being. One should maintain positive attitude to something is the way that we think and feel about it. Our attitude expresses positive and negative feelings about some objects. Good working attitude is important to attain success in one's life. Developing a positive attitude means interpreting life's events in a way that is truthful, honest and self-affirming. We can develop enthusiasm, optimism, adaptability, confidence, self-control and self-esteem. Our attitude speaks so much of who we are either professionally or personally. One has to remember that in our life the things just not happen accidentally. Everything that we come across is incidental. One has to have clear picture of what one wants.

Our behavior is the act we act in general, especially in relation to the situation they are in or the people they are with. Our behavior is influenced by culture, attitude, emotions, values, ethics, authority and genetic factors. Our behavior should be with easiness and tolerance. Our personal behavior has a great impact on our career, business, goals, health and relationships. It helps in building self-esteem, improving self-confidence and develops a professional

personality that will enhance our personal growth. So, developing and maintaining a good professional personality and behavior is important.

The third one is Character which is the most essential one in our life. Character refers to the sum of an individual's qualities and characteristics which differentiate him/her from others. An individual's character is actually an amalgamation of his/her qualities which makes him unique and helps him stand apart from the rest. It is also about developing one's inner self and being a good human being. Character is something which comes from within and is often long lived. A good character helps you develop a winning personality. In other words, a good character is the backbone of a magnetic personality which attracts other people. As there is an old saying that Money we wasted, opportunity we missed, arrow that is shot, character that is lost are never going to get back again. The duty of every individual is to strengthen his character with the help of parents, teachers or guides. Teachers play a very crucial role. They help in shaping character and also act as role models to achieve those personal goals that they have already walked through. An individual with a good character would in turn have a good personality.

Discipline is needed in every aspect. To work or to learn in every aspect, discipline is very important. The important types of disciplines are Physical discipline, Mental discipline, Social discipline and Economic Discipline. We have to do physical exercises to keep healthy and fit to gain Physical Discipline. Mental discipline is to maintain mind in a state of balance. No one has the need to be aggressive and regressive. God did not made us to be oppressed, depressed or suppressed. We have to maintain tranquility. Having a balanced state of mind is of utmost importance to an individual.

Social discipline is achieved by respecting every being and encouraging everyone. We should not judge or condemn everyone. Economic discipline is to earn honestly and spend wisely. If we spend wisely whatever we get is enough for our livelihood. Spiritual discipline includes regular and constant remembrance of God and regular practice of rituals. These are the basic concepts to form the strong foundation of one's career and life.

These life skills or soft skills or basic skills are the deciding factors in personality development. In addition to this, soft skills is a range of abilities ncluding work ethics, courtesy, teamwork, self-discipline and self-confidence, professional presence, language proficiency, cultural sensitivity, communication skills, ability to accept and learn from criticism, ability to handle client relationships, networking, creativity, ability to motivate yourself and lead others, time management, leadership and interpersonal skills. Soft skills play an important role in the development of the students' overall personality, thereby enhancing their career prospects. The soft skills training provides strong practical orientation to the students and helps them in building and improving their skills in communication, the effective use of English, business correspondence, presentations, team building, leadership, time management, group discussions, interviews, and inter-personal skills.

Soft skills are essentially people skills-- the non-technical, intangible, personality-specific skills that determine one's strengths as a leader, speaker, listener, negotiator, and conflict mediator. It means skills related to human attitude, team work, leadership qualities, over all human nature enhancements. The combination of characteristics or qualities that form an individual's distinctive character is the literal meaning of Personality. The definition of Personality in Psychology is to refer to individual differences in characteristic patterns of thinking, feeling and behaving. Personality development is the development of the organized

pattern of behaviors and attitudes that makes a person distinctive. Personality development occurs by the ongoing interaction of temperament, character, and environment. If we heat gold then only it gives beautiful ornament, the beaten copper becomes wire; depleted stone only can become a statue. So the more pains we get the more valuable they become. Our attitude, behavior and character will change the pains and makes us successful in all the fields. If we are able to follow these in our daily life, our mind will be strengthened, we can understand any aspect of the subject easily and thoroughly within the given time or even in the less time.

We can communicate with anybody and our knowledge will double to the progress. We can succeed in any sort of interview and we will be asset in any organization. One has to remember that every successful person has a painful story and every painful story has a successful ending.

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